

Illustrated Technical Paper - A Electric Network Reconfiguration Strategy with Case-based Reasoning for the Smart Grid

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Abstract

This "**ILLUSTRATED TECHNICAL PAPER**" presents the slides describing the contents of the paper "A Electric Network Reconfiguration Strategy with Case-based Reasoning for the Smart Grid".

The talk was presented at the **8th Brazilian Conference on Intelligent Systems - BRACIS 2019**, 15 - 18 October 2019 at Salvador, Brazil.

The "illustrated technical paper format" is intended to complement, enrich and subsidize the technical paper content and contains slides, complementary text and additional and/or focused bibliographic references.

Index Terms

Smart Grid, Grid Reconfiguration, Case-based Reasoning, HATSGA, Cognitive Management, Autonomy, Self-healing, Scalability, On-the-fly Computation.

1 PAPER ABSTRACT

The complexity, heterogeneity and scale of electrical networks have grown far beyond the limits of exclusively human-based management at the Smart Grid (SG). Likewise, researchers cogitate the use of artificial intelligence and heuristics techniques to create cognitive and autonomic management tools that aim better assist and enhance SG management processes like in the grid reconfiguration. The development of self-healing management approaches towards a cognitive and autonomic distribution power network reconfiguration is a scenario in which the scalability and on-the-fly computation are issues. This paper proposes the use of Case-Based Reasoning (CBR) coupled with the HATSGA algorithm for the fast reconfiguration of large distribution power networks. The suitability and the scalability of the CBR-based reconfiguration strategy using HATSGA algorithm are evaluated. The evaluation indicates that the adopted HATSGA algorithm computes new reconfiguration topologies with a feasible computational time for large networks. The CBR strategy looks for managerial acceptable reconfiguration solutions at the CBR database and, as such, contributes to reduce the required number of reconfiguration computation using HATSGA. This suggests CBR can be applied with a fast reconfiguration algorithm resulting in more efficient, dynamic and cognitive grid recovery strategy.

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2 PAPER SLIDES

A Electric Network Reconfiguration Strategy with Case-Based Reasoning for the Smart Grid

Flávio Galvão Calhau and Joberto S. B. Martins

Fig. 1.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:**

This article presents the the use of Case-based Reasoning (CBR) coupled with the HATSGA algorithm for achieving fast reconfiguration of large distribution power networks [1].

Results suggest that CBR can be applied with a fast reconfiguration algorithm resulting in more efficient, dynamic and cognitive grid recovery strategy

-- > **Paper to read:**

- The full paper text describing the Case-based Reasoning reconfiguration strategy is "**A Electric Network Reconfiguration Strategy with Case-based Reasoning for the Smart Grid**" and is available at:

- * ARXIV: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1907.05885>

- * ZENODO: <https://zenodo.org/record/3277283#.XbHiHehKgdU>

- * Research Gate: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/334329987_A_Electric_Network_Reconfiguration_Strategy_with_Case-Based_Reasoning_for_the_Smart_Grid

-- > **Complementary papers describing Smart Grid concepts and electrical network reconfiguration:**

- Smart Grid concepts and standardization aspects are described in: [2] [3]

Agenda

- Introduction
- Related work
- Cognitive strategy proposal
- Validation
- Final considerations

Fig. 2.

Objective

Conception of a cognitive framework with autonomic characteristics (CBR-SGRec) for electrical network reconfiguration which offers scalability in the dynamic search for new solutions for the Smart Grid.

Fig. 3.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:**

"This paper proposes the use of Case-Based Reasoning (CBR) coupled with the HATSGA algorithm for achieving fast reconfiguration of large distribution power networks. The motivation is to develop a CBR-based framework with cognitive self-healing characteristics for the distribution network aiming the reduction of human intervention in the recovery process."

Context

Smart Grid – A solution for the electrical system

- A **smarter** network (synthetic vision for the electrical system)
- Requires **computer networks** supporting electrical networks/electrical systems
- New features (systems) must be introduced into the electrical system

More sensors, more automation in processes, operation style with bidirectional flow of data (operator $\leftarrow \rightarrow$ client), other innovations

- Use of new ICT with a more systemic and global approach to addressing problems in Smart Grid

Control/Administration by human beings

Fig. 4.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:**

"Smart Grid represents a modern vision of a dynamic electricity grid, in which electricity and related information flow together in real time, allowing near-zero economic losses in the event of outages and power quality disturbances. All of this being supported by a new energy infrastructure built on top of communication channels, distributed intelligence and possibly clean power [4]."

"Current electricity grids are highly heterogeneous, have to deal with an exponential growth in the number of users, are highly dynamic in terms of user's demands and are subject to failure [5]. Either in case of failure or to allow maintenance maneuver and optimization, the network must be reconfigured as rapidly as possible."

Electrical Network Reconfiguration

Supports the decision making process, planning and / or control of operation of electrical networks.

Consists of finding, among all possible combinations, a configuration that:

- minimizes the number of interconnect key opening operations (radiality);
- performs load balancing;
- improves voltage levels;
- reduces the loss of electricity; and
- reduces the number of consumers without electricity supply.

Fig. 5.

- **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:**

"The use of artificial intelligence to create cognitive distribution power network reconfiguration management tools that aim better assist and enhance the SG distribution network reconfiguration processes is an important research issue [6]."

"In addition to the artificial intelligence component, fast algorithms are also necessary to compute new distribution network reconfiguration. In effect, the overall distribution power network reconfiguration solution must scale to be adequate for on-the-fly utilization in large grid deployments, like the ones existing in Smart Cities."

Related Work

- In general, the proposals discussed before do not take into account solutions that reach the objectives with a minimum (or no) human intervention, which is one of the focuses of this proposal
- The proposals presented typically deal with a specific existing heuristic or specific algorithms to implement the process of reconfiguration of the electrical distribution network
- They do not use the capabilities of machine learning and autonomic computing

Fig. 6.

— > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:**

"In recent years, significant research has been done to minimize power loss in the process of reconfiguring distribution power systems. The reconfiguring of distribution power system has a combinatorial nature and the search of the best computational time for supporting the decision-making process in real time has been focused on [7], [8], [9] [10]."

"Tabu search algorithm has been used for several combinatorial optimization solutions [11] [12] and [13]. In [12] Tabu search is used as a meta-heuristic method for network reconfiguration problem in radial distribution systems. In [13] is proposed a method of network reconfiguration using a modified Tabu search algorithm focusing on reducing keys opening and closing and minimizing the loss. The HATSGA algorithm proposes an enhanced Tabu list to compute only more relevant data and reduce the computation time [14]."

"In [15] the authors implement an algorithm for network reconfiguration for a realistic distribution network based on a genetic algorithm (GA), taking as objective power loss minimization and load balancing index. HATSGA uses a distinct genetic algorithmic approach by using elitism to choose among potential solutions."

General View – Autonomic and Cognitive Computing

Cognitive Computing

- Simulate the processes of human thought in a computational model, characterized by non-supervised learning capacities
- Basic features (Kelly, 2017):
 - Generate and evaluate various solutions;
 - Evaluate responses based on relevant evidence and/or business rules;
 - They provide specific guidance for the situation, focused on decision-making;
 - Improve knowledge and learn from each iteration and interaction.

Fig. 7.

Case-based Reasoning (CBR)

Seek a similar solution to a current problem, by establishing degrees of similarity with a past experience, stored in the Knowledge Base (Wangenheim, 2003).

Fig. 8.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:**

"Case-Based Reasoning (CBR) is a machine learning technique for problem solving that solves new problems using the experience acquired with previous cases [16]. CBR functions as a cognitive model that allows to imitate humans to solve real problems by remembering previously solved cases (problems) that are used to suggest a solution for novel but similar situation."

"In CBR one case is a stored pair with a problem and a solution used to solve this problem in the past. Thus, the cases (C_i) are composed of problems encountered in the network (P_i) and the solution to such problems (S_i)."

CBR Cycle Steps

Figure: CBR Cycle - Adapted from [Aamodt A.; Plaza 1994].

Fig. 9.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:**

"CBR workflow in the CBR-SGRec framework follows the classical 4R sequence (Figure 4) [16]."

"The process is triggered by an existing problem (new case). A similar case is searched in the CBR database using an appropriate similarity function and an adaptation is done if necessary. The solution is applied and, later validated for retention in the solutions CBR database."

"One of the reasons for the use of similarity follows the hypothesis that similar problems must have similar solutions [17]. There are many ways of evaluating similarity with different approaches for different case representations [18]."

Fig. 10.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:**

"The conceptual CBR-based Smart Grid network recovery framework (CBR-SGRec) is illustrated in Figure 10. The basic CBR-SGRec framework components are:

- The smart grid distribution network;
- A monitoring system collecting grid operation parameters;
- A knowledge plan; and
- An actuation system capable to deploy new reconfiguration topologies on the the network."

"The CBR-SGRec framework knowledge plane includes the basic elements of the CBR strategy:

- A knowledge database containing possible network reconfiguration solutions;
- The CBR engine analyzing, planning and acting on behalf of the network reconfiguration process; and
- The network reconfiguration algorithm to be called whenever required."

HATSGA Algorithm (CALHAU, F. et al, 2015) (CALHAU, F. ; MARTINS, J., 2017)

The HATSGA is a hybrid algorithm that seeks to optimize the process of reconfiguration of electrical networks using as a basis the strategy of the Tabu Search (TS) incorporating the selection phase pertinent to genetic algorithms.

Fig. 11.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:**

"HATSGA is an algorithm aimed to compute power distribution reconfiguration solutions in the Smart Grid context [14]. HATSGA uses graph theory with language "R" to model the distribution network. HATSGA uses only radial topologies and reduces the search space to minimize power flow evaluation and to reduce the computational algorithm effort required."

"HATSGA's strategy minimizes the search space solution by eliminating topology configurations that do not comply with constraints criteria like radial configuration, voltage profile and system loss."

"HATSGA uses elitism, a technique inspired by evolutionary biology and natural selection [19]. Elitism is used by HATSGA to select potential topologies that can be used to compute new reconfiguration solutions by selecting electrical parameters that may result in the computation of new minimal solutions for power loss."

HATSGA Algorithm (CALHAU, F. et al, 2015) (CALHAU, F. ; MARTINS, J., 2017)

```

Ler informações da topologia
Gera uma população inicial  $S_o \leftarrow$  Solução Inicial
 $P_a \leftarrow$  Energia ativa de  $S_o$ 
 $Min \leftarrow P_a$ 
 $K_o \leftarrow$  Chaves manipulável de  $S_o$  for each  $K_o$  do
    |  $switch = 1$  (Fechar chave)
    | Busca de ciclo
    |  $Listc \leftarrow$  Lista de ciclos
end
for cada ciclo em  $Listc$  do
    | Escolher as chaves baseado no processo de seleção
    |  $Listps \leftarrow$  Lista de chaves escolhidas pelo elitismo
end
Criar  $TL$  (Lista tabu) for cada topologia gerada pela condição da chave em  $Listps$  do
    | if não existe em  $TL$  then
    |   | Atualiza  $TL$ 
    |   | Calcula  $P_a$  (Nova perda ativa) if  $P_a < Min$  then
    |   |   |  $Min \leftarrow P_a$ 
    |   |   end
    |   end
end
end

```

Fig. 12.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:**

"The summary of HATSGA algorithm phases are as follows:

- HATSGA generates a radial topology network as an initial topology using the minimum spanning tree (cs), calculate the power loss (bs) for this topology through the power flow calculation based on Newton-Raphson and build a tabu list (TL) with the initial configuration (status of open edges).
- From (cs), all the open switches (edges) are stored in a vector (ns). For each switch in ns, changed the status "closed", creating a loop in the current topology (cs).
- Use elitism (where n of the best candidates in each generation are taken to the next generation) to select the topologies that have a greater probability of success to be part of the solution and these are in store vector ns'.
- for each switch in ns', the switch is open undoing the loop. The loss power of the new topology is calculated. If the new topology is not yet stored in the tabu list (TL), it is added.
- If the power loss bs' of the new computed topology is lower than the previously stored (bs), the best solution is updated.
- After checking all existing sectorial loops, power loss bs of the solution is updated with the best topology."

Validation

Implementation:

- "R" Language with the Igraph package
- Protégé – A framework for the construction of intelligent systems
- MyCBR-Software Development Kit (SDK) for information retrieval based on similarity

Evaluated aspects are:

- Reduce electrical losses in the process of network reconfiguration;
- Evaluate the computational time required to calculate the solutions;
- Verify the scalability of the HATSGA algorithm;
- Evaluate the process of recovery and learning of CBR-SGRec solutions.

Fig. 13.

-- > PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:

"The CBR module was implemented using the Protégé [20] and MyCBR [21] tools. Protégé is a free, open-source ontology editor and framework for building CBR systems. MyCBR is an open-source similarity-based retrieval tool and software development kit (SDK). The network topology used in the proof-of-concept was the IEEE-14Bus."

"The Protégé configured parameters to evaluate similarity were "pesoploss" used to show the system loss ratio topology similarity, the "pesoprofileV" that represents the accumulate load-flow in the system voltage profile and "pesoprofileVQtd" that represents the number of buses of the nominal value. A similarity threshold and similarity parameter priority may also be defined for the CBR module. that exceeded the limit"

Simulation Parameters

Parameters evaluated by HATSGA:

- Loss of active energy in the system busbars
- Computational time of execution of the HATSGA
- Scalability of the algorithm with increased network complexity

Parameters used by HATSGA:

- Radial topology
- Heuristic for research solution-COH
- Power Flow Method-Newton-Raphson
- Priority

Other parameters:

- IEEE topologies (14Bus and 300Bus)
- EPM Matrices
- VPM Matrices

Fig. 14.

"In terms of the proof of concept, a fault is simulated eliminating buses 9 and 11 at the current topology. A global similarity of 92% is defined, no priority is assigned to the similarity parameters and an alert is sent to the CBR-SGRec framework."

"The framework is flexible and can be adjusted by the manager to look for similar cases according to established priorities. If, for instance, the manager opted for cases giving priority to attribute "pesoprofileVQtd", the CBR module retrieves another set of cases up to 94% of similarity. In this simulation, three "best" cases have the same similarity. So the manager could choose the retrieve case combining priorities with more than one attributes to assist in the decision-making process."

Evaluation 5 – Scalability Test (CALHAU, F. ; MARTINS, J., 2019) 3

Scalability Test x Scalability Test HATSGA

Topologia IEEE	Tempo Médio de Solução (s)	Desvio padrão	IC (95%)	Topologia IEEE	Tempo Médio do HATSGA (s)	Desvio padrão	IC (95%)
16-Bus	0.2551	0.0218	[0.2482 : 0.2620]	16-Bus	0.1827	0.0190	[0.1767 : 0.1887]
14-Bus	0.4466	0.3518	[0.4361 : 0.4570]	14-Bus	0.2350	0.0206	[0.2289 : 0.2411]
33-Bus	1.2505	0.1300	[1.2131 : 1.2879]	33-Bus	0.4001	0.0383	[0.3891 : 0.4111]
69-Bus	2.9524	0.3583	[2.8502 : 3.0545]	69-Bus	0.6143	0.0435	[0.6019 : 0.6267]
57-Bus	7.6239	0.9098	[7.3691 : 7.8786]	57-Bus	1.3207	0.1333	[1.2834 : 1.3580]
118-Bus	34.0414	5.3780	[32.5395 : 35.5433]	118-Bus	5.0643	1.1253	[4.7500 : 5.3785]
300-Bus	816.5329	46.5311	[792.9216 : 840.1443]	300-Bus	22.4069	1.3906	[21.7013 : 23.1125]

Fig. 15.

"HATSGA algorithm, as a figure of merit, gets minimum power loss results that is equivalent to the best result obtained by this algorithm described in [22] and [23]."

Evaluation 06 – CBR-SGRec (CALHAU, F. ; MARTINS, J., 2019)

Cases on the knowledge databas (14Bus)

TopologyIndex	Opened Switch(es)	System Loss	pesoploss	pesoprofileV	pesoprofileVQtd
Topology:1	c(1, 4, 5, 9, 11, 15, 19)	6.4601	1.519809	119.886	8
Topology:2	c(7, 4, 5, 9, 11, 15, 19)	10.2323	2.407260	103.516	6
Topology:3	c(6, 4, 5, 9, 11, 15, 19)	10.3816	2.442385	105.920	8
Topology:4	c(1, 6, 5, 9, 11, 15, 19)	7.7666	1.827177	129.892	8
Topology:5	c(1, 3, 5, 9, 11, 15, 19)	5.8164	1.368372	113.756	8
Topology:6	c(1, 3, 7, 9, 11, 15, 19)	6.199	1.458382	102.186	6
Topology:7	c(1, 3, 4, 9, 11, 15, 19)	5.0418	1.186138	120.857	8
Topology:8	c(1, 3, 4, 7, 11, 15, 19)	4.5208	1.063567	11.623	7
Topology:9	c(1, 3, 4, 13, 11, 15, 19)	4.8242	1.134946	111.364	8
Topology:10	c(1, 3, 4, 10, 11, 15, 19)	5.0418	1.186138	1.285	4
Topology:11	c(1, 3, 4, 17, 11, 15, 19)	66.1695	15.567096	2.921	6
Topology:12	c(1, 3, 4, 7, 16, 15, 19)	4.5626	1.073401	5.592	6
Topology:13	c(1, 3, 4, 7, 13, 15, 19)	4.3581	1.025291	188.069	8
Topology:14	c(1, 3, 4, 7, 18, 15, 19)	4.5628	1.073448	49.540	7
Topology:15	c(1, 3, 4, 7, 13, 8, 19)	4.3581	1.025291	21.356	6
Topology:16	c(1, 3, 4, 7, 13, 9, 19)	4.3581	1.025291	13.500	8
Topology:17	c(1, 3, 4, 7, 13, 15, 16)	4.3518	1.023808	7.258	7
Topology:18	c(1, 3, 4, 7, 13, 15, 18)	4.3521	1.023879	18.486	8
Topology:19	c(1, 3, 4, 7, 13, 15, 11)	4.31	1.013974	29.652	8
Topology:20	c(1, 3, 4, 7, 13, 15, 12)	4.2927	1.009904	16.552	7
Topology:21	c(1, 3, 4, 7, 13, 15, 17)	4.2506	1.000000	19.190	9

- **pesoploss** used to show the similarity of system topology power loss
- **pesoprofileV** representing the accumulated charge flow in the system voltage profile
- **pesoprofileVQtd** representing the number of bars that exceeded the nominal value limit.3

Fig. 16.

Evaluation 06 – CBR-SGRec (CALHAU, F. ; MARTINS, J., 2019)

In simulation, to trigger CBR-SGRec, faults are simulated.

Buses 9 and 11 in the current IEEE 14-Bus topology.

Fig. 17.

Evaluation 06 – CBR-SGRec (CALHAU, F. ; MARTINS, J., 2019)

In simulation, to trigger CBR-SGRec, faults are simulated.

Buses 9 and 11 in the current IEEE 14-Bus topology.

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Topology:5	c(1, 3, 5, 9, 11, 15, 19)	5.8164	1.368372	113.756	8
Topology:6	c(1, 3, 7, 9, 11, 15, 19)	6.199	1.458382	102.186	8
Topology:7	c(1, 3, 4, 9, 11, 15, 19)	5.0418	1.186138	120.857	8
Topology:8	c(1, 3, 4, 7, 11, 15, 19)	4.5208	1.063567	11.623	7
Topology:9	c(1, 3, 4, 13, 11, 15, 19)	4.8242	1.134946	111.364	8
Topology:10	c(1, 3, 4, 10, 11, 15, 19)	5.0418	1.186138	1.285	4
Topology:11	c(1, 3, 4, 17, 11, 15, 19)	66.1695	15.567096	2.921	6
Topology:12	c(1, 3, 4, 7, 16, 15, 19)	4.5626	1.073401	5.592	6
Topology:13	c(1, 3, 4, 7, 13, 15, 19)	4.3581	1.025291	188.069	8
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Topology:15	c(1, 3, 4, 7, 13, 8, 19)	4.3581	1.025291	21.356	6
Topology:16	c(1, 3, 4, 7, 13, 9, 19)	4.3581	1.025291	13.500	8
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Topology:18	c(1, 3, 4, 7, 13, 15, 18)	4.3521	1.023879	18.486	8
Topology:19	c(1, 3, 4, 7, 13, 15, 11)	4.31	1.013974	29.652	8
Topology:20	c(1, 3, 4, 7, 13, 15, 12)	4.2927	1.009904	16.552	7
Topology:21	c(1, 3, 4, 7, 13, 15, 17)	4.2506	1.000000	19.190	9

QUERY RESULTS

1	Topology:7... 0.94	0.94
2	Topology:5... 0.94	0.94
3	Topology:1... 0.94	0.94
4	Topology:4... 0.93	0.93
5	Topology:3... 0.93	0.93
6	Topology:6... 0.86	0.86
7	Topology:2... 0.85	0.85

Start: 10:58:10
Finish: 10:58:10
Duration: 0,001 sec

Priority is assigned to the pesoprofileVQtd parameter

Fig. 18.

Evaluation 06 – CBR-SGRec (CALHAU, F. ; MARTINS, J., 2019)

In simulation, to trigger CBR-SGRec, faults are simulated.

Buses 9 and 11 in the current IEEE 14-Bus topology.

Fig. 19.

Evaluation 07 – CBR-SGRec (CALHAU, F. ; MARTINS, J., 2019)

No case in the Knowledge Database (30Bus)

Topology	Opened Switch(es)	System Loss	pesoploss	pesoprofileV	pesoprofileVQtd
Topology 1	c(4, 7, 9, 14, 15, 18, 20, 22, 29, 33, 39, 40)	16.1671	2.53860406689173	356.023	21
Topology 2	c(4, 3, 9, 14, 15, 18, 20, 22, 29, 33, 39, 40)	15.6569	2.45849101044202	154.537	22
Topology 3	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 20, 22, 29, 33, 39, 40)	14.5007	2.27694119494386	46.867	21
Topology 4	c(4, 6, 8, 14, 15, 18, 20, 22, 29, 33, 39, 40)	14.9327	2.34477506477192	85.616	23
Topology 5	c(4, 6, 7, 11, 15, 18, 20, 22, 29, 33, 39, 40)	116.856	18.3490617884902	3.939	20
Topology 6	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 26, 20, 22, 29, 33, 39, 40)	14.6981	2.30793750490696	95.273	22
Topology 7	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 28, 20, 22, 29, 33, 39, 40)	14.6574	2.30354667504122	11.114	21
Topology 8	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 21, 20, 22, 29, 33, 39, 40)	14.7043	2.30891104655727	449.976	21
Topology 9	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 19, 20, 22, 29, 33, 39, 40)	14.6608	2.30208051272042	592.596	22
Topology 10	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 26, 22, 29, 33, 39, 40)	14.4916	2.27551228703776	142.882	21
Topology 11	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 28, 22, 29, 33, 39, 40)	14.4509	2.26912145717202	58.348	20
Topology 12	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 21, 22, 29, 33, 39, 40)	14.4978	2.27648582868807	58.62	21
Topology 13	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 19, 22, 29, 33, 39, 40)	14.4543	2.26965533485122	29.518	22
Topology 14	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 31, 22, 29, 33, 39, 40)	14.4576	2.27017351024574	8.486	21
Topology 15	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 28, 24, 29, 33, 39, 40)	14.4732	2.2726230666562	447.969	21
Topology 16	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 28, 26, 29, 33, 39, 40)	14.4765	2.27314124205072	661.223	21
Topology 17	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 28, 23, 29, 33, 39, 40)	14.4858	2.27460155452618	344.945	22
Topology 18	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 28, 21, 29, 33, 39, 40)	14.4827	2.27411478370103	56.416	19
Topology 19	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 28, 19, 29, 33, 39, 40)	14.4393	2.26729999214886	331.277	20
Topology 20	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 28, 19, 27, 33, 39, 40)	14.3319	2.25043573839994	362.114	22
Topology 21	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 28, 19, 31, 33, 39, 40)	14.3915	2.25979430007066	287.783	22
Topology 22	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 28, 19, 27, 41, 39, 40)	14.2841	2.24293004632174	161.016	22
Topology 23	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 28, 19, 27, 24, 39, 40)	14.3246	2.24928947161812	593.288	20
Topology 24	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 28, 19, 27, 23, 39, 40)	14.3372	2.25126795948811	338.539	20
Topology 25	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 28, 19, 27, 30, 39, 40)	14.3081	2.24668859464552	222.508	20
Topology 26	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 28, 19, 27, 25, 39, 40)	14.2612	2.23933422312947	226.443	22
Topology 27	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 28, 19, 27, 35, 39, 40)	14.3117	2.24809609798226	116.121	22
Topology 28	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 28, 19, 27, 22, 39, 40)	14.3023	2.24578786213394	7672.893	21
Topology 29	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 28, 19, 27, 25, 37, 40)	14.2059	2.23065085970009	5383.64	22
Topology 30	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 28, 19, 27, 25, 38, 40)	14.132	2.21904687131978	414.213	22
Topology 31	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 28, 19, 27, 25, 38, 10)	14.0212	2.20164873989165	625.369	22
Topology 32	c(4, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 28, 19, 27, 25, 38, 41)	14.0765	2.21033210332103	702.419	22

Simulated Failures.

Buses 4 and 15 in the IEEE 30-Bus topology.

CBR-SGRec does not find a suitable case for solving the problem, the HATSGA algorithm is triggered to find a solution.

Fig. 20.

Evaluation 07 – CBR-SGRec (CALHAU, F. ; MARTINS, J., 2019)

Figure: Solutions found by HATSGA

Fig. 21.

Evaluation 07 – CBR-SGRec (CALHAU, F. ; MARTINS, J., 2019)

Topology	Opened Switch(es)	System Loss	pesoploss	pesoprofileV	pesoprofileVQid
Topology 1	c2, 3, 8, 10, 14, 18, 19, 20, 29, 30, ...	13.0277	2.0456465415717986	358.2830000000001	24
Topology 2	c4, 3, 8, 10, 14, 18, 19, 20, 29, 30, ...	15.6985	2.4650231608699062	660.7989999999999	20
Topology 3	c7, 3, 8, 10, 14, 18, 19, 20, 29, 30, ...	15.8823	2.493883960116197	203.445	20
Topology 4	c1, 3, 8, 10, 14, 18, 19, 20, 29, 30, ...	11.0446	1.7942545340347022	1808.6950000000002	23
Topology 5	c1, 7, 8, 10, 14, 18, 19, 20, 29, 30, ...	11.5548	1.814367504844154	306.3350000000001	24
Topology 6	c1, 6, 8, 10, 14, 18, 19, 20, 29, 30, ...	10.108	1.5871869356991444	218.38799999999995	24
Topology 7	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 18, 19, 20, 29, 30, ...	9.6759	1.5193373635864018	293.9669999999999	21
Topology 8	c1, 6, 9, 10, 14, 18, 19, 20, 29, 30, ...	9.8956	1.5538352830336815	485.721	23
Topology 9	c1, 6, 7, 41, 14, 18, 19, 20, 29, 30, ...	9.7312	1.5280202770157806	201.091	19
Topology 10	c1, 6, 7, 40, 14, 18, 19, 20, 29, 30, ...	9.7868	1.536751197299207	361.255	22
Topology 11	c1, 6, 7, 10, 11, 18, 19, 20, 29, 30, ...	9.6759	1.5193373635864018	39.68200000000001	24
Topology 12	c1, 6, 7, 10, 12, 18, 19, 20, 29, 30, ...	9.6759	1.5193373635864018	10.112000000000002	23
Topology 13	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 24, 19, 20, 29, 30, ...	9.87	1.5498154981549814	68.71499999999999	24
Topology 14	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 9, 19, 20, 29, 30, ...	9.5134	1.4938211509774673	374.32800000000003	22
Topology 15	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 8, 19, 20, 29, 30, ...	9.7258	1.52717280364293	323.703	23
Topology 16	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 23, 19, 20, 29, 30, ...	9.8826	1.5517939860249665	178.68800000000002	24
Topology 17	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 3, 19, 20, 29, 30, ...	8.7836	1.3792258773651567	136.64400000000003	21
Topology 18	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 19, 20, 29, 30, ...	8.8882	1.0816047734945435	219.933	23
Topology 19	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 24, 20, 29, 30, ...	6.9222	1.0869435502865668	182.04400000000004	24
Topology 20	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 26, 20, 29, 30, ...	6.9255	1.087461256810866	76.91199999999999	23
Topology 21	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 23, 20, 29, 30, ...	6.9347	1.0889063358718694	148.894	24
Topology 22	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 21, 20, 29, 30, ...	6.7281	1.0564654157179871	789.8849999999999	24
Topology 23	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 21, 20, 29, 30, ...	6.9317	1.0884352673313968	559.518	24
Topology 24	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 18, 24, 29, 30, ...	6.7157	1.054518324173668	157.534	24
Topology 25	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 18, 26, 29, 30, ...	6.7191	1.0550522100965691	78.59499999999998	16
Topology 26	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 18, 23, 29, 30, ...	6.7283	1.0564968202873517	58.61900000000001	16
Topology 27	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 18, 21, 29, 30, ...	6.7252	1.0560100494621967	140.87699999999998	24
Topology 28	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 18, 19, 29, 30, ...	6.6818	1.0491952579100259	245.68400000000003	24
Topology 29	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 18, 19, 27, 30, ...	6.5744	1.0323310041611053	330.693	24
Topology 30	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 18, 19, 28, 30, ...	6.6274	1.0406532150427887	68.72699999999999	16
Topology 31	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 18, 19, 27, 24, ...	6.5909	1.034921881133705	114.87899999999999	23
Topology 32	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 18, 19, 27, 23, ...	6.6035	1.03690036900369	297.37499999999994	23
Topology 33	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 18, 19, 27, 28, ...	6.5535	1.0290492266624793	171.5	24
Topology 34	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 18, 19, 27, 31, ...	6.5602	1.0301012797362017	223.828	23
Topology 35	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 18, 19, 27, 28, ...	6.5206	1.0238831750019628	132.27700000000002	24
Topology 36	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 18, 19, 27, 28, ...	6.5612	1.0302583025830259	311.894	23
Topology 37	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 18, 19, 27, 28, ...	6.5737	1.0322210881683285	532.32300000000001	24
Topology 38	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 18, 19, 27, 28, ...	6.5446	1.02765172323257438	341.37999999999998	24
Topology 39	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 18, 19, 27, 28, ...	6.4977	1.0202873518096882	659.1719999999999	23
Topology 40	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 18, 19, 27, 28, ...	6.5388	1.0267409908141636	118.88800000000002	24
Topology 41	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 18, 19, 27, 28, ...	6.4425	1.011619690649917	137.071	24
Topology 42	c1, 6, 7, 10, 14, 5, 18, 19, 27, 28, ...	6.3685	1	266.174	24
Topology 43	c4, 6, 8, 14, 15, 18, 20, 22, 29, 33, ...	14.9327	2.34477506477192	85.616	23

Figure: Result of the learning process of the CBR-SGRec framework.

The new solution to the network reconfiguration problem encountered if it meets the established rules or is validated by the network manager is learned by the CBR-SGRec framework.

Fig. 22.

Conclusion

- This paper presents a cognitive strategy that uses Case Based Reasoning (CBR) coupled with the HATSGA algorithm for rapid reconfiguration of large power grids in the context of Smart Grid.
- The proposed strategy uses a problem solving methodology that relies on the human cognitive system for both reasoning and learning.
- The uniqueness of the proposal is to actively add a cognitive strategy with autonomic characteristics associated with the process of monitoring and acting in the network reconfiguration process in order to reduce the response time in the search for solutions as well as minimize human presence in the process.

Fig. 23.

"This paper presented the CBR-SGRec framework that uses Case-Based Reasoning (CBR) coupled with the HATSGA algorithm for fast reconfiguration of large distribution power networks in the Smart Grid context."

"The CBR-SGRec framework is cognitive and has the capability to compute new network reconfiguration topologies nearly on-the-fly."

The cognitive characteristic of CBR-SGRec is supported by the CBR module that, firstly, reduces the time required to compute new network configurations by finding out similar previously used solutions. Secondly, CBR module is capable to learn and incorporate new knowledge to its database by keeping new successful reconfiguration."

Contributions

- The conception of a cognitive strategy for the problem of network reconfiguration dynamically and with autonomy.
- Development of HATSGA algorithm aimed at reconfiguring smart grids.
- Scalability in the search for solutions in large networks.
- Modular and flexible framework for cognitive management of electrical networks.

Fig. 24.

"In summary, the use of the CBR machine learning technique within the CBR-SGRec framework has proven possible to have a decision-making tool supporting the reconfiguration management process in the Smart Grid. This approach fundamentally reduces the human intervention for a rather complex management task requiring accurate engineering knowledge."

THANKS!

Fig. 25.

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